

STUDIES ON COMPLEX CARBONATES OF URANIUM BY THERMOMETRIC AND CONDUCTOMETRIC METHODS

BY BARUN CHANDRA HALDAR

Both thermometric and conductometric methods indicate the existence in solution of the compounds of the type $R_1UO_2(CO_3)_3$ and $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ (where $R=Na$ or K).

Literature on complex carbonates of uranium with alkali carbonates shows only the existence of the compounds $K_1UO_2(CO_3)_3$ (Aloy, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1901, vii, 24, 412 ; Ebelmen, *ibid.*, 1842, vii, 5, 189) and $Na_2UO_2(CO_3)_3$ (Anthon, *Dingl poly. J.*, 1860, 156, 207, 288) but no mention of the compounds of the type $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ (where $R=Na$ or K) is found. It is expected from the very close analogous behaviour of the uranyl radical (UO_2^{++}) with other bivalent transitional metals that it should also have a compound of the type $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ or $R_2CO_3.UO_2.CO_3$, as in the case of other bivalent transitional metals reported by Reynold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 263) and others. In the present investigation attempts have been made to obtain indications of the existence of the compounds $K_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ and $Na_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ by physico-chemical methods such as thermometric and conductometric titrations of uranyl salts with alkali carbonate solutions and *vice versa*.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric arrangement is the same as that has been described in a previous paper (Haldar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 147).

Conductivity Apparatus.—The arrangement is in principle a Wheatstone bridge. The A. C. was provided by a valve oscillator of the Hartley type giving an accurately determined frequency, free from harmonics. The sharpness of the minimum was increased by replacing the telephone by a vacuum tube amplifier. The earphone was then connected in the plate circuit of the vacuum tube.

Uranyl nitrate solution was estimated as U_3O_8 by evaporating 10 c.c. of the solution in a platinum crucible on a water-bath and the residue was then heated in a full flame of the Meker burner until the weight of the crucible was constant. Alkali nitrate solutions were estimated as sulphate. All conductometric titrations were carried out in an electrically controlled thermostat, the temperature of which could be adjusted correct to 0.1° . Solutions for conductometric titrations were prepared in twice-distilled water.

Thermometric Titrations

TABLE I

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.4100M ; 40 c.c. of 0.0202M-Na₂CO₃ soln.

Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.090	0.000	0.000	11 c.c.	3.570	-0.07	0.485
1	3.950	.080	.080	12	.640	-.070	.395
2	.880	.090	.170	13	.710	-.070	.325
3	.795	.095	.265	14	.790	-.080	.325
4	.680	.080	.345	16	.920	-.130	.245
5	.600	.080	.425	18	.965	-.045	.115
6	.520	.080	.505	20	.855	+.010	.070
7	.495	.035	.540	22	.945	+.010	.080
8	.495	.000	.540	24	.925	+.020	.090
9	.495	.000	.540	26	.905	+.020	.110
10	.500	-0.005	.535				.130

TABLE II

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.205M ; 40 c.c. of 0.101M-Na₂CO₃ soln.

Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.990	0.000	0.000	10.0 c.c.	3.720	0.000	0.270
1	.950	.040	.040	11.0	.750	-0.030	.240
2	.900	.050	.090	12.0	.780	-.030	.210
3	.860	.040	.130	13.0	.810	-.030	.180
4	.820	.040	.170	14.0	.840	-.030	.150
5	.775	.045	.215	16.0	.900	-.060	.090
6	.730	.045	.260	18.0	.920	-.020	.070
6.5	.720	.010	.270	20.0	.920	-.000	.070
7.0	.720	.000	.270	22.0	.910	.010	.080
8.0	.720	.000	.270	24.0	.900	.010	.090
9.0	.720	.000	.270	26.0	.890	.010	.100
9.5	.720	.000	.270				

TABLE III

Na₂CO₃ soln. = 0.9807M ; 40 c.c. of 0.1004M-Uranyl nitrate soln.

Vol. Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Vol. Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	2.100	0.000	0.000	10 c.c.	1.935	0.035	0.165
1	.180	-.080	-.080	11	.910	.025	.190
2	.240	-.060	-.140	12	.890	.030	.220
3	.285	-.045	-.185	13	.865	.015	.235
4	.320	-.035	-.220	14	.850	.015	.250
5	.320	-.000	-.220	16	.820	.030	.280
6	.215	.105	-.115	14	.805	.015	.295
7	.115	.100	-.015	20	.790	015	.310
8	.040	.075	.060				
9	1.970	.070	.013				

TABLE IV

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.1942*M* ; 40 c.c. of 0.08786*M*-K₂CO₃ soln.

Vol. of uranyl nitrate soln. added	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Vol. of uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.530	0.000	0.000	10 c.c.	4.290	-0.01	0.240
1	.490	.040	.040	11	.310	-0.02	.220
2	.440	.050	.090	12	.340	-0.03	.190
3	.390	.050	.140	13	.370	-0.03	.160
4	.350	.040	.180	14	.395	-0.025	.136
5	.305	.045	.225	16	.420	-0.025	.110
6	.280	.025	.260	18	.430	-0.010	.100
7	.280	.000	.250	20	.430	-.00	.100
8	.280	.000	.250	22	.430	-.00	.100
9	.280	.000	.250				

TABLE V

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.38835*M* ; 40 c.c. of 0.1757*M*-K₂CO₃ soln.

Vol. uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	Vol. uranyl nitrate soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.860	0.000	0.000	9 c.c.	3.485	-0.020	0.375
1	.790	.070	.070	10	.495	-.010	.365
2	.715	.075	.145	11	.520	-.025	.340
3	.640	.075	.220	12	.540	-.020	.320
4	.570	.070	.290	13	.580	-.010	.310
5	.500	.070	.360	14	.565	-.015	.295
6	.450	.050	.410	16	.620	-.055	.240
7	.450	.000	.410	18	.710	-.080	.150
8	.465	-.015	.395	20	.790	-.080	.070

TABLE VI

K₂CO₃ soln. = 1.5254*M* ; 40 c.c. of 0.1942*M*-Uranyl nitrate soln.

K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.230	0.000	0.000	10 c.c.	3.640	0.110	0.690
1	.300	-.070	-.070	11	.520	.120	.710
2	.340	-.040	-.110	12	.450	.070	.780
3	.350	-.010	-.120	13	.400	.050	.830
4	.350	-.000	-.120	14	.360	.040	.870
5	.330	.020	-.100	15	.320	.040	.910
6	.270	.060	-.040	16	.290	.030	.940
7	.085	.205	.165	18	.220	.070	1.010
8	.680	.185	.350	20	.170	.050	1.060
9	.760	.130	.480	22	.120	.050	1.110

TABLE VII

K₂CO₃ soln. = 0.78705M ; 40 c.c. of 0.09708M-Uranyl nitrate soln.

K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.	K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.580	0.000	0.000	10 c.c.	4.135	0.080	0.445
1	.590	-.010	-.010	11	4.040	.095	.540
2	.605	-.015	-.025	12	3.990	.050	.59
3	.605	-.000	.025	13	.950	.040	.63
4	.580	.025	.000	14	.915	.035	.665
5	.555	.025	.025	15	.885	.030	.695
6	.510	.045	.070	16	.855	.030	.725
7	.410	.100	.170	18	.800	.065	.78
8	.310	.100	.270	20	.750	.050	.83
9	.215	.095	.365	22	.710	.040	.87

Conductometric Titrations

TABLE VIII

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 50 c.c. of 0.0103M ; Na₂CO₃ soln. = 2M. Temp. = 27° ± .1°

Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0 c.c.	103 mho	0.280 c.c.	105.1 mho	0.530 c.c.	168.4 mho	0.795 c.c.	236.1 mho
0.05	98	.320	109.7	.575	171.5	.840	249.3
.12	99	.360	117.0	.620	184.5	.930	272.5
.16	99.9	.405	127.5	.665	194.9	1.015	284.9
.20	101.7	.450	138.5	.710	209.2	1.100	305.9
.235	103.9	.490	146.6	.750	223.7		

TABLE IX

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.5M. 50 c.c. of 0.01M-K₂CO₃ soln. = Temp. = 27° ± .1°

Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	118.3 mho.	0.465 c.c.	101.0 mho.	0.740 c.c.	104.0 mho.
.99	114.8	.510	101.4	.840	111.1
.185	111.1	.560	101.4	.935	119.7
.275	107.5	.605	102.2	1.020	128.2
.370	102.7	.650	102.2	1.110	136.7
.415	101.4	.695	102.7	1.200	144.7

TABLE X

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 50 c.c. of 0.01 M. K₂CO₃ soln. = 2 M. Temp. = 27° ± .1°

K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	K ₂ CO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	104.0 mho.	0.245 c.c.	123.8 mho.	0.510 c.c.	196.3 mho.	0.845	328.3 mho.
.075	105.3	.320	134.6	.585	225.2	0.920	356.6
.150	112.7	.395	156.7	.655	254.2	1.025	394.0
.220	121.2	.465	179.2	.750	290.6	1.120	430.8

TABLE XI

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 0.5M ; 50 c.c. of 0.01 M-Na₂CO₃ soln. Temp. = 27° ± .1°

Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	Uranyl nitrate soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0.00 c.c.	99.2 mho.	0.395 c.c.	89.3 mho.	0.875 c.c.	99.0 mho.
.08	97.3	.440	89.1	.770	91.3
.17	95.6	.490	89.2	.860	98.9
.26	93.2	.540	89.3	.950	102.9
.305	92.0	.590	89.2	1.045	110.8
.355	90.4	.630	89.8	1.230	125.9
				1.405	140.8

TABLE XII

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 50 c.c. of 0.01M. KNO₃ soln. = 1 M. Temp. = 27° ± .1°

KNO ₃ soln. added	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	KNO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	KNO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	KNO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	104.7 mho.	0.790	166.0 mho.	0.885 c.c.	210.01 mho.	1.360 c.c.	265.3 mho.
.105	117.0	.580	177.0	1.015	223.02	1.510	278.6
.240	134.2	.700	190.5	1.135	234.58	1.690	299.9
.335	145.4	.795	202.3	1.260	253.31	1.840	317.4
						1.990	331.4

TABLE XIII

Uranyl nitrate soln. = 50 c.c. of 0.01M. NaNO₃ soln. = 1M. Temp. 27° ± .1°

NaNO ₃ soln. added	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	NaNO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	NaNO ₃ soln. added	1/R × 10 ⁴ .	NaNO ₃ soln. added.	1/R × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	mho.	0.520 c.c.	139.1 mho.	1.010 c.c.	191.9 mho.	1.680 c.c.	248.1 mho.
.110	105.8	.680	155.2	1.190	202.6	1.850	265.3
.220	115.5	.790	169.0	1.320	219.6	1.985	381.0
.350	126.6	.900	181.9	1.500	232.7		294.0

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the curves shown below that carbonates of the type $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_3$ and $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ both exist. The breaks in the thermometric curves appear at the

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

FIG. 7.

points corresponding to uranyl nitrate : alkali carbonate equal to 1:3 and 1:2 over the concentration range studied. Moreover, the breaks are always obtained at the same points either by adding alkali carbonate solutions to uranyl nitrate solutions or *vice versa*. In conductometric titration curves, breaks corresponding to $R_4UO_2(CO_3)_2$ and $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ appear exactly at the equivalent points only when the alkali carbonate solutions are added to uranyl nitrate solutions (Fig. 4). But in reverse titrations i.e., when uranyl nitrate solutions are added to alkali carbonate solutions (Fig. 5-6), the two breaks are not exactly at the points corresponding to $R_4UO_2(CO_3)_2$ and $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$ but slightly shifted. The exact cause of the shifting in the curves (Fig. 5-6) is difficult to say with certainty but it may be due to the complex nitrate formation. Conductometric titrations of uranyl nitrate with alkali nitrates show indication of complex formation of the type $R_2UO_2(NO_3)_4$, where $R=Na$ or K . Although the breaks in curves (Fig. 7-8) are not very sharp, they are always found to occur at the point corresponding to uranyl nitrate : alkali nitrate equal to 1:2. Literature on complex nitrates of uranium nitrate with alkali nitrates describe only the potassium compound $K_2UO_2(NO_3)_4$, and not the sodium compound. However, to explain the discrepancy observed in the curves 9 and 11 and the difference in the slopes of the curves 4 and 5, further investigation is needed

FIG. 8.

Break due to basic carbonate of indefinite composition is also found to occur in the curves (Fig. 1-5). Thus with thermometric and conductometric evidences on the existence of the carbonates of the type $R_2UO_2(CO_3)_2$, the uranyl radical (UO_2) shows close analogy with other bivalent transitional metals particularly with respect to complex carbonate formation. The author's best thanks are due to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, Dr. Es. So., F.N.I., for his keen interest, helpful suggestions and all laboratory facilities during the progress of the work.

GROSS PROFESSOR'S CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 17, 1947.